

Silver nanowire composite electrodes for semitransparent organic solar cells

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Abstract

Semitransparent organic photovoltaics (OPV) are emerging as a key technology for agrivoltaic systems, as they can transmit light within the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) range due to their wavelength-selective absorption properties. Their light weight, non-toxicity, and mechanical flexibility also make them well suited to agricultural applications, such as in greenhouses and foil tunnels.^[1] However, large-area, low-cost production of such modules is currently hindered by the need to produce highly transparent and conductive liquid-processed electrodes, which could replace the expensive and technically challenging indium-tin oxide (ITO) sputtering and silver evaporation processes ^[2]. Here, we present a fully blade-coated silver nanowire (AgNW) electrode that meets the electrical and optical requirements of semitransparent OPV, and which can be adapted directly to large-area, roll-to-roll coating processes. The electrode consists of a composite of AgNWs and organic conductive polymers, fabricated via multiple coating steps. It fulfils the requirements of sheet resistance of under 10 Ωsq^{-1} and optical transmittance of over 80% in the spectrum relevant for agrivoltaics (370–740 nm). Based on this electrode, we

have developed blade-coated, halogenated-solvent-free organic solar cells with an ITO/ZnO/PTQ10:BTP-FTh/electrode architecture, which have exceptional fill factors and an LUE_{APT} of 3.5%.

References

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- [2] Fu Yang et al., Large-area flexible organic solar cells, *npj Flexible Electronics* 2021, 5, 30.

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Figure: Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of a silver nanowire electrode.